

Green and blue space quality metrics scoping review

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Executive Summary

Green and blue spaces provide benefits across a range of elements of environment and society. However, conceptualising green and blue spaces as uniform in quality and function does not account for the ability the space itself to deliver these benefits. Understanding how quality of green and blue spaces is measured in relation to the multifunctionality of these spaces will therefore contribute to improving management, policy, and decision making.

We have carried out a scoping review of English language grey and academic literature on green and blue space quality, with the objectives to:

1. Identify which quality indicators are currently being used for green and blue spaces;
2. Understand how multifunctionality of green and blue space is being captured in quality metrics.

From an initial 2079 unique papers identified, 83 were included in the final review. Most studies we identified were conducted in the UK, followed by Germany and Poland. We identified a total of 68 indicators of green and blue space quality, with over 80% of indicators associated with the environment or people category. Coverage overall was good for both green and blue spaces, and across space types and habitats, in urban and rural locations, highlighting the wide applicability of green and blue space quality metrics. However, urban locations were covered slightly more than rural locations, and no indicators were used in only rural locations. A future focus on quality particularly for rural green and blue space may therefore be beneficial to ensure equity in access to quality green and blue spaces.

Multifunctionality was widely considered, with capitals either measured alongside each other, integrated into a single capital measure, or concerned with the impact of one capital on another. We do not make judgement as to which method of combination is preferred, as different situations will suit different considerations of multifunctionality. The scale considered in the papers which considered multifunctionality ranged from single identified green and blue spaces to green and blue spaces across whole countries. The consideration of scale is significant, and indeed at the individual green or blue space level multifunctionality may not be desirable and may detract from the purpose of a space, while multifunctionality across city-wide green and blue spaces is important for wellbeing.

The outcomes of this review will go on to inform workshops and interviews with green and blue space managers and business users, carried out in summer 2023, with the eventual production of a green and blue space cost-benefit analysis toolkit at the end of 2027. For more information or to be involved in future research please contact: Michaela.roberts@hutton.ac.uk.

Introduction

Green and blue spaces, urban and rural, are vital to the health of our communities, economies, and environment. They are so important for our health and wellbeing that increasing access to the outdoors is a Scottish Government National Performance Framework indicator. Encouraging, managing, and investing in outdoor access has cross-sectoral policy significance relating to health, planning, environment, education, and tourism. However, conceptualising green and blue spaces as uniform in quality and function does not account for the ability the space itself to deliver these functions. Recent work on the benefits of urban greenspace has identified quality as of more importance than quantity (Dobson et al., 2019). Despite ongoing interest in the characterisation of the spatial qualities of green and blue spaces, definitions and indicators of green and blue space quality are seldom uniform. Understanding how quality of green and blue spaces is measured in relation to the multifunctionality of these spaces will therefore contribute to improving management, policy, and decision making to produce better outcomes.

Green and blue spaces provide benefits across a range of elements of environment and society. The “Four Capitals” approach provides a lens through which to conceptualise these benefits, and has been applied by the Scottish Government in relation to post-Covid recovery (Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020). The Four Capitals are defined as:

- Environment – Natural Capital: nature’s stock of natural assets.
- Community – Social Capital: shared understandings that enable cooperation.
- People – Human Dimension: health, skills, and knowledge accumulated by individuals.
- Business – Economic Capital: products of human productive activities.

We have applied this lens to understanding the benefits from green and blue space, although noting that differentiation between each capital may not be clear cut in all cases (i.e., some services may arguably be placed in multiple capitals).

Scoping reviews have a wider remit than traditional literature reviews, intending to understand the breadth of the literature, rather than in-depth study of a narrower field. They are often applied to clarify concepts and identify gaps in understanding, and go on to inform larger bodies of work (Munn et al., 2018). We carried out a scoping review with the following objectives:

1. Identify which quality indicators are currently being used for green and blue spaces, with particular focus on outcomes for the “Four Capitals”(Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020):
 - a. Environment – natural capital (potential indicators: biodiversity, water, air, soil)
 - b. Community – social capital (potential indicators: group meeting spaces, demonstration of shared values)
 - c. People – Human capital (e.g. health and wellbeing potential indicators: gym equipment, air quality)
 - d. Business – financial capital (potential indicators: cafes, nature tours)
2. Understand how multifunctionality of green and blue space is being captured in quality metrics.

In this report we consider publicly accessible green (e.g., public parks, forests) and blue (e.g., coastal waters, rivers). Although private green and blue spaces can provide complimentary services to those provided by public spaces (Hanson et al., 2021), they are not under the control of public bodies, and therefore options for impacting management is limited.

The outcomes of this review will go on to inform workshops and interviews with green and blue space managers and business users, carried out in summer 2023, with the eventual production of a green and blue space cost-benefit analysis toolkit at the end of 2027. For more information or to be involved in future research please contact: Michaela.roberts@hutton.ac.uk.

Methods

We conducted a scoping review of English language grey and academic literature on green and blue space quality published within the last 5 years. Academic literature was sourced from Web of Science and grey literature from websites of 22 organisations involved in green and blue space management within Scotland, and the Scottish Government (For full list see (Roberts et al., 2022)). We considered evidence from countries with similar biomes (Kaplan et al., 2003) and cultures as Scotland: United Kingdom, Ireland, Norway, The Netherlands, Belgium, Germany, Denmark, Luxemburg, France, Austria, and Poland. For full details see (Roberts et al., 2022).

Green and blue space was defined in collaboration with project funders (Scottish Government Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division) as: “vegetated areas and blue spaces in both urban and rural areas, including woodland, parks, farmland, paths and beaches and other aquatic environments that are publicly accessible”.

We considered quality in terms of direct contribution of green and blue space to the Four Capitals (Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020):

- Environment: Natural capital – stock of natural assets, including soil, air, water and biodiversity which may occur in, or be influenced by, green and bluespace;
- Community: Social capital – networks, shared experience, values and understanding which may occur in, or be influenced by, green and blue space
- People: Human capital – health and wellbeing accumulated through green and blue space use or as a result of green and blue space in the surrounding area (e.g. air quality is improved as a result of nearby green and blue space, regardless of whether an individual actively uses it)
- Business: Economic capital – monetary gain through green or blue space use or association

Documents were screened first by title and then by abstract to ensure they met the eligibility criteria (i.e. are papers in English which include measurement of green and blue space quality, are within the defined geographical area, consider analysis of data and are not lab-based studies). Information on greenspace types, categorised according to Planning Advice Note 65 (Scottish Government, 2008), bluespaces type, habitat (Butcher et al., 2020), location, and quality indicators was recorded from all retained documents. Where possible information was also extracted on the population for whom quality was measured, testing of the quality indicators in terms of their accuracy in representing the quality for which they were intended (e.g. number of benches as an indicator of accessibility), and the integration of indicators for multiple capitals.

Results

General

From an initial 2079 unique papers identified, 83 were included in the final review (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Screening record of scoping review. For full list of grey literature searched see protocol.

Most studies we identified were conducted in the UK, followed by Germany and Poland. Within UK, evidence predominantly came from England, and nearly one quarter of UK studies were from Scotland (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Summary of studies by location. Note Spain is outside of geographical scope, but the two papers included Spain within a wider group of countries and so have been included here.

Overall, nearly twice as many studies were conducted in urban areas compared to rural areas. This ratio remained stable across the four capitals, though there were fewer community studies in rural areas than urban areas. There were no studies conducted in island areas (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Summary of studies conducted in urban/rural/island areas in total and for each capital. Total capitals = green bars; Environment = blue bars; Community = orange bars; People = grey bars; Business = yellow bars. A single study could be conducted in more than one setting.

Overall, more studies examined quality indicators of greenspace than bluespace, across capital types. A study could examine quality indicators of both greenspace and bluespace.

Within greenspace natural or semi-natural greenspace received most attention; public park or garden and play space were also often examined. Among all types of green space, civil received least attention, apart from “other functional greenspace” (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Summary of studies by types of greenspace in total and for each capital. Total capitals = green bars; Environment = blue bars; Community = orange bars; People = grey bars; Business = yellow bars. A study could examine quality indicators for more than one type of greenspace.

Within bluespaces most studies examined running water and standing water (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Summary of studies (percentage) by types of bluespace in total and for each capital. Total capitals = green bars; Environment = blue bars; Community = orange bars; People = grey bars; Business = yellow bars. A study could examine quality indicators for more than one type of bluespace.

With regards to habitat, quality indicators for heathland and scrub, grassland, and wetland were most often examined (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Summary of studies by types of habitats in total and for each capital. Total capitals = green bars; Environment = blue bars; Community = orange bars; People = grey bars; Business = yellow bars. A study could examine quality indicators for more than one type of habitat.

The majority of studies did not identify a population for which they were testing quality. This pattern is consistent across capital types. Only a minority of studies tested the green or bluespace quality indicators.

Quality indicators

Environment

There are 29 indicators of environmental quality, with at least one indicator in both urban and rural environments, all the green and blue space categories and all the habitat categories. Seven indicators are used at least once in all green and blue space and habitat categories: Biodiversity – species diversity, size and number of trees, ecological connectivity, diversity of terrain, regulation of ecological quality, noise pollution and hemeroby/naturalness. Allergenic potential was the only environmental indicator to not be used in any bluespace categories. Water quality – disease causing bacteria was the only environmental indicator to not be used in any of the greenspace categories (Table 1). Most indicators are used in both urban and rural environment, only two of the indicators look at only urban areas (allergenic potential and NDVI). There were three that looked at only built up habitats, the rest were used in more than one habitat. These three are: NDVI, allergenic potential and air pollution. While few individual studies test indicators, all but five of the indicators are tested in at least one study. The five non-tested indicators are: biodiversity – species richness, NDVI, physical structure, allergenic potential and carbon storage (Table 1).

The populations quality indicators were used in could be grouped into either populations of a specific geographical area, such as a city or a specific bluespace area; or in a specific population group, such as churchgoers or Welsh river swimmers. Most individual studies did not identify a population, but across studies all but six environment indicators did have an associated population.

Table 1 Environment quality indicators

Indicator	Description of what is measured	Was the indicator: Used in Greenspace
Green/bluespace area	The size of the green or blue space	
Biodiversity - generic	Overall biodiversity	
Biodiversity - species richness	The number of species	
Biodiversity - species abundance	The number of individuals of a species	
Biodiversity - species diversity	The number of species relative to number of individuals.	
Vegetation cover	The vegetation or plant cover of the green or blue space	
NDVI	The NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index)	
Size and number of trees	The tree size and number in the green or blue space	
Protected area	The presence of protected areas within the green or blue spaces	
Protected plants/animals	The presence of any protected plant or animal or key species	
Ecological connectivity (inc. edge diversity index)	How ecologically connected different areas studied were, including their edge diversity, mean patch size and connectivity, functionality as an ecological corridor, and unfragmented open space.	
Physical Structure	The forest or terrain structure of the green or blue space	
Diversity of terrain	The diversity of the terrain or topography	
Pollination potential	The amount of pollination or seed dispersal possible in an area	
Water quality - generic	The generic water quality	
Water quality – disease causing bacteria	The human disease potential of water, for example the presence of E-coli	
Water quality - nutrient	The presence of nutrients in the water, such as nitrates, phosphorous or ammonia	
Water flow & discharge	The flow or discharge of water in a green or blue space	
Regulation of ecological quality	The ability of the green or blue space to regulate certain ecological functions	
Soil conservation	The quality of soil and provisions for conserving soil	
Temperature	The land, soil, air or water temperature of the green or blue space	
Noise pollution	The excessive noise load	

Air pollution	The air pollution, PM10 and NO2 etc	
Allergenic potential	The potential to add to allergies	
Presence of wildlife	The presence of wildlife	
Presence of water	The presence of water	
Hemeroby/ naturalness	The naturalness or the hemeroby index (an index of naturalness/human interference), genuineness of the landscape	
Integration with landscape	How the green or blue space fits with the surrounding area	
Carbon storage	The amount of carbon stored in or sequestered by green or blue space	

People

There are 28 indicators of quality for people, and, as with the environment category, there is at least one indicator covering urban and rural environments, all the green and blue space categories and all the habitat categories. Further, accessibility – generic, uniqueness, and recreation – recreation facilities are used in all categories (Table 2). Duration of time spent in green/bluespace was not used in any bluespace. Seven of the quality for people indicators have only been used in urban areas. These are duration of time spent in green/bluespace, accessibility – barriers, accessibility – for those with a disability, aesthetics generic, aesthetics vegetation, physical health and indexes of multiple deprivation. Duration of time spent in green/bluespace, physical health, and indexes of multiple deprivation covered only built up habitats.

The majority of indicators were tested in at least one study, only three indicators were not tested: duration of time spent in green/bluespace, accessibility – barriers, and accessibility – for those with a disability. Similar to the environmental indicators the populations used are either populations of a specific geographical area, such as a city or a specific bluespace area; or in a specific population group, such as children. There is only one indicator, recreation – recreation facilities, that does not identify any of the populations in which it is used in.

Table 2 People quality indicators

Indicator	Description of what is measured	Was the indicator: Used in Greenspace
Duration of time spent in Greenspace/Bluespace	The duration of time spent in green or blue spaces	
Frequency of visits to G/BS	The frequency of visits to a green or blue space	
Accessibility - generic	The general accessibility, with no specific reference to whether it was about internal or external accessibility (covered below)	
Accessibility - internal	The accessibility within the green or blue space, such as paths	

Accessibility - getting there	The accessibility to the green or blues space, such as public transport and cycle lanes	
Accessibility - proximity	How close the green or blue space as to people	
Accessibility - barriers	The presence of barriers to accessing the green or blue space	
Accessibility - for those with a disability	Whether there was any provision for disabled access	
Aesthetics - generic	The general aesthetics, where no mention of specific types of aesthetic covered in other indicators	
Aesthetics - Maintenance, well kept, management, cleanliness	The maintenance and management, cleanliness and upkeep of the green of blue space	
Aesthetics - View	The quality of the view in terms of aesthetics	
Aesthetics - Vegetation	The aesthetics of the vegetation in green or blue space	
Incivilities	The presence of incivilities, including graffiti, vandalism, dog fouling and litter	
Uniqueness	The rareness or distinctiveness of the landscape	
Safety	The safety and security of an area	
Services - generic	The presence of services in general, without any mention of specific types of services covered below and in later sections	
Services - people	The presence of non-recreational services that enabled people to use the space	
activities	The presence of activities in the green or blue space with no specific reference to what activities were carried out	
Education/Learning potential	whether there were spaces or potential for learning present, often focused on children	
Physical health	The impact of the green or blue space on physical health	
Physically activity	Whether the green or blue space enabled physical activity	
Recreation – recreation facilities	The presence of recreation facilities or spaces for recreation	
Recreations – Sports facilities	The presence of sports facilities such as tennis courts or sports pitches	
Mental wellbeing	The impact of the green or blue space on mental health or wellbeing	
Spiritual wellbeing	The impact the green or blue space had on feeling calm, tranquil, or at peace. It was used in urban and rural environments	

Connection to nature	The connection to nature produced by being within the green or blue space. It was used in urban and rural environments	
Quietness	The quietness of the area, not feelings of quietness as this is covered by spiritual wellbeing	
Indexes of multiple deprivation	The index of multiple deprivation (IMD) or Scottish index of multiple deprivation (SIMD) of the green or blue space	

Community

Although having only six quality indicators, community quality indicators still cover both urban and rural environments, all the green and blue space categories and all the habitat categories. However, no single indicator covered all the categories on its own. Only the indicator of spiritual quality was not tested (Table 3). This indicator was also the only community indicator to not be used in rural environments, and was used only in built up habitats. Spiritual quality was not considered in any bluespace. Similar to the environmental and people indicators the populations used are either populations of a specific geographical area, such as a city or a specific bluespace area; or in a specific population group, such as children. All the community indicators had at least one population identified that they were used in.

Table 3 Community quality indicators

Indicator	Description of what is measured	Was the indicator: Used in Greenspace
Services - community	The presence in green or blue space of services, which are viewed as specific objects (e.g. Picnic tables) or spaces (e.g. Meeting spaces), that enable the community to gather	
Children's play	The ability of children to play in the green or blue space, often through the presence of a playground	
Cultural	The presence of anything cultural within the green or blue space, such as open-air theatres or art	
Historical	The presence of anything historical within the green or blue space such as historical monuments	
Spiritual	The presence of anything spiritual or religious within the green or blue space	
Social interaction	Whether the green or blue space enabled: people to connect, social interactions, social relations, or social inclusion	

Business

Across the five business indicators both urban and rural environments, all the green and blue space categories and all the habitat categories are covered by at least one indicator. One indicator, services – business, covered all these categories. Unlike the other capital categories, all indicators looked at both urban and rural environments, and both green and blue space. There was only one

indicator, flood risk, that was not tested (Table 4). Similar to the other capital indicators the populations used are either populations of a specific geographical area, such as a city or a specific bluespace area; or in a specific population group, such as children. All the business indicators had identified a least one population that they were used in.

Table 4 Business quality indicators

Indicator	Description of what is measured	Was the indicator: Used in Greenspace
Services - business	The presence of services that are important for, or are, a business, such as cafes	
Tourism potential	The impact of the green or blue space for tourism	
Financial benefits	The possible financial gains available through the green or blue space	
Flood risk	The potential flood risk or damage within a green or blue space	
house price	The property and land value within the green or blue space	

Multifunctionality

We are considering multifunctionality particularly in relation to the Four Capitals introduced above. A study was considered to be measuring multifunctional quality if it incorporated indicators from more than one capital. Multiple capitals were considered in 53% of studies. Environment and people were most often considered together, with environment, people and community the most common where three capitals were considered (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Percentage of papers which include each capital in combination. There were no papers looking at community and business, environment and community, or community, people and business.

We did not find any existing framework to assess multifunctionality in measuring green and blue space quality, and so therefore developed categorisation based on the documents reviewed which incorporated multiple capitals. We identified three ways in which multifunctionality was considered:

- Multiple capitals measured alongside each other;
- Multiple capitals used to create a single quality metric;
- Quality of one capital impacting another.

These categorisations are not intended to be a judgement on suitability for assessing multifunctionality, but to demonstrate different ways in which it can be achieved.

Multiple capitals measured alongside each other

Having individual indicators which measure different capitals, with no further integration, was the most common method for incorporating multifunctionality into green and blue space quality assessments. This included assessment of the ways in which spaces were used, such as children observed playing with peers and taking part in biology lessons (Aalbers and Sehested, 2018). Studies have also used observations of the attributes of a space as an indicator of multifunctional quality. In a study of beach and river quality in Wales ability to see sea life and river water quality were used to indicate the environmental quality of the space, while accessibility and suitability for recreation are used to indicate quality for people. These attributes were then used in a travel cost model of coastal and beach visits (Anciaes, 2022). Other studies have looked at features of church gardens (Kaczyńska, 2020), used existing spatial datasets to map features over large areas (Liu and Russo, 2021), or surveyed users to identify urban greenspace features (Krellenberg et al., 2021). Surveys of users have also been used to identify greenspace features and feelings associated with greenspaces in relation to multiple capitals (Barlow et al., 2021). Specific areas or types of greenspace have been assessed for contributions to different capitals. In Germany forestry was assessed for its contribution to environment through considering its tree species diversity, presence of large trees and deadwood, as well as for its potential for recreation through its species and structural diversity, and stand management and density (Biber et al., 2021).

In some instances studies have specifically sought out complementary disciplines to assess multifunctionality, as was carried out in Denmark for planning land consolidation (Johansen et al., 2018). Less commonly used was assessment of policy documents to identify indicators of different capitals used (Carmen et al., 2020). In one study the ability of products from the greenspace, in this case honey, to provide benefits across environment and people was also included (Affek, 2018). Specific frameworks mentioned include the socio-cultural values framework (Edwards, 2022).

Multiple capitals combined to a single quality measure

The multiple functions of green and blue spaces can be combined to create a single quality measure. Green infrastructure which must deliver to multiple functions, such as water management, nature conservation and health and wellbeing (Calvert et al., 2018), or ecological and social benefits (Sowińska-Świerkosz et al., 2021) has been measured in this way. A single combined metric has also been used to assess the quality of therapeutic spaces for children in learning environments, where a single space needs to meet the health and wellbeing needs of individuals, as well as the community needs of an education setting (Chiumento et al., 2018). Similarly this approach has been used to compare the health benefits of urban areas in Paris (Trojanowska, 2019). Single quality measures can be particularly useful when comparing qualities of green and blue spaces over larger use areas, such as between municipalities (Kuta et al., 2020), across National Parks (Sowińska-Świerkosz and Michalik-Śniezek, 2020) or to consider natural capital across an area (O’Keeffe et al., 2022; Stebbings et al., 2021). This is often carried out for green and blue spaces assessed via satellite imagery (Thiele et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019). Specific tools include the Natural Environment Testing Tool (Gidlow et al., 2018), RECITAL (Knobel et al., 2021), and Green and Open Space Factor Vienna (Ring et al., 2021).

Quality of one capital impacting another

Capitals may be considered not just alongside each other, but also for the impacts they have on one another. This has most often been done for impacts on health and wellbeing, such as tree and flower planting on older mobility (Benton et al., 2018), or greenspace (Brindley et al., 2019; Dennis

et al., 2020) or bluespace (Mishra et al., 2020) quality on general health. Other studies have also considered factors such as attachment (Boyer et al., 2019) or activities conducted (Fongar et al., 2019). It is important with this category to be aware of potential reverse causality, where the capitals considered may have impacts on each other. Greenspace quality for example, may increase social deprivation, however social deprivation may also mean that fewer funds are available to invest in improving greenspace quality (Baka and Mabon, 2022).

Discussion

We identified a total of 68 indicators of green and blue space quality, with over 80% of indicators associated with the environment or people category. Coverage overall was good for both green and blue spaces, and across space types and habitats, in urban and rural locations, highlighting the wide applicability of green and blue space quality metrics. However, urban locations were covered slightly more than rural locations, and no indicators were used in only rural locations. A future focus on quality particularly for rural green and blue space may therefore be beneficial to ensure equity in access to quality green and blue spaces.

The comparatively low number of indicators relating to the community and business categories may indicate that they are less often conceptualised in relation to green and blue spaces than quality for the environment or for people. Community and business were also more often considered in combination with people and/or environment than alone. This may support the idea that community and business are less often associated with green or blue spaces than environment or people and are included most often when multifunctionality is being explicitly measured. Community and business functions may also more often be provided by alternative spaces (e.g., high streets for businesses, community halls for community connections). It may also be harder to conceptualise what 'quality' for these services looks like. In the case of community, the elements that create networks are often intangible, and may relate to a 'feeling' or common understanding that is not easily explained even by those experiencing it. For businesses being sited in or near a green or blue space may only form part of their business model, and therefore the impact of the quality of the space may be hard to untangle. As urban populations grow pressures for green and blue spaces to deliver functions previously supported by other spaces may increase. Future work on these wider, less understood qualities for green and blue spaces will provide opportunity to inform the development and management of outdoor spaces to meet these developing needs.

Although less than half of the individual papers tested the quality metrics they applied, the majority of indicators were tested by researchers at least once. Although we did not consider the outcomes of the testing of these indicators (i.e., we do not know whether the testing indicated they were a good indicator), it is encouraging that the majority of indicator were tested. This is useful for thinking about the future usability of the indicators, as a tested indicator is more reliable, although care must be taken to understand under what circumstances the indicator has been tested, and one indicator may not be suitable in all situations.

Most papers did not identify the populations for which they were testing quality. This could be a concern as to the validity of the quality being measured, as not everyone considers quality in the same way, and different users may have different priorities in the space. Failing to identify the population for whom quality is measured therefore runs the risk of reducing quality as perceived by segments of the population of users, or failing to identify optimal management strategies to maximise benefits. Populations which were identified were either geographically bounded, such as

users of a particular green or blue space, or residents of a city; or a particular group of the population, such as children, or those with a disability. Future work should prioritise identifying for whom they are measuring quality.

Multifunctionality was widely considered, with capitals either measured alongside each other, integrated into a single capital measure, or testing the impact of one capital on another. We do not make judgement as to which method of combination is preferred, as different situations will suit different considerations of multifunctionality. The scale considered in the papers considered multifunctionality ranges from single identified green and blue spaces to green and blue spaces across whole countries. The consideration of scale is significant, and indeed at the individual green or blue space level multifunctionality may not be desirable and may detract from the purpose of a space. For example, a wildlife pond may contribute only to the environment through biodiversity and provide no services to business. Similarly, a tennis court may only provide benefits to people through improving health but have negligible biodiversity impact. The value of such spaces would be reduced were they to try to cater to all needs. However, at a wider scale, such as across a neighbourhood, city or country, access to green and blue spaces that cover the range of environment, community, people, and business needs is important. Scale may prove particularly important when considering how to measure multifunctionality. Combining into a single metric has the advantage of being able to compare different green and blue spaces easily and on a level playing field, but can lose the nuance of exactly what each space is providing. This type of multifunctionality may therefore be better suited to larger areas. However, when considering individual green and blue spaces within a neighbourhood considering capitals alongside each other will enable the details of individuals spaces to be retained. This would ensure that valuable single-use spaces are not unfairly penalised.

Next steps

We have presented here prospective green and blue space quality indicators as identified from the literature. In the next stage of the research, we will run a survey followed by two workshops (Summer 2023) with green and blue space managers, policy makers, and business users from urban and rural areas to validate the quality indicators for the Scottish context. These indicators will later go on to form the basis of a green and blue space cost-benefit analysis toolkit, for investing in quality green and blue space (2024-2027).

To express an interest in involvement in the survey or workshops in summer 2023 please contact: Michaela.roberts@hutton.ac.uk.

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